

Comprehensive Method Development and Validation of RP-HPLC for Molnupiravir Quantification in Medicinal Dosage Forms

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Abstract

Molnupiravir has been granted emergency use authorization status by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to treat mild-to-moderate COVID-19 in adults who have tested positive for the virus via direct SARS-CoV-2 viral testing. The aim of this research endeavor was to develop and validate a RP-HPLC (Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography) technique that could accurately measure the concentration of molnupiravir in pharmaceutical dosage forms. The study centered on the careful refinement of chromatographic parameters, employing a Thermo Fisher Scientific HS-C18 column as the immobile phase. The solvent system, which be made up of a solution containing H₂O: ACN (70:30 % V/V), was carefully preferred. It was circulated at a rate of 1.0 ml/min. This validation encompassed various considerations including linearity, accuracy, precision, sensitivity, specificity, and selectivity. The chromatographic condition modifications yielded results that showcased the accuracy, speed, accuracy, and sensitivity of the method, hence guaranteeing dependable analysis of Molnupiravir. The RP-HPLC process that was developed was subjected to comprehensive validation in accordance with the guidelines set forth by the International Council for Harmonization (ICH). The HPLC method for assay of molnupiravir was successfully developed, validated, and demonstrated to be accurate, robust, specific, and stability indicating. The verified RP-HPLC method is a reliable instrument utilized in pharmaceutical formulations for regular quality monitoring. It provides a direct and economical method for estimating molnupiravir for routine analysis in QC laboratories would save significant time, resources and solvents.

Keyword: Molnupiravir, RP-HPLC, Method Development, Validation, stability indicating

1. Introduction

Viruses are the pinnacle of parasitism. In addition to consuming the nutrients of the host cell, they regulate its metabolic processes in order to generate more virions. As a result, viral chemotherapy was taken into account. It is impossible since it would require interfering with the cellular metabolism of the host. Over the last half-century, it has been demonstrated that the infected cell does, in fact, contain enzymes that are specific to the virus. Furthermore, some viruses possess a limited number of enzymes that exhibit greater affinity towards particular inhibitors or antimetabolites compared to enzymes found in healthy cells. Additionally, pharmaceutical compounds have been developed to selectively inhibit viral maturation, assembly, reverse transcription, cell penetration, and coating removal [1].

In addition to gamma and delta, the two genera of corona viruses that harbour pathogenic viruses that are susceptible include alpha and beta. Significant illness can be caused by seasonal coronaviruses, such as OC43, HKU1, 229E, and NL63, although this occurs seldom but frequently in immunocompromised patients [2]. The ability to cause disease, known as pathogenicity, is a key characteristic of sarbo viruses like SARS-CoV, SARS-CoV-2, and MERS-CoV. The SARS-CoV virus is accountable for inducing severe acute respiratory syndrome. Nevertheless, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has shown that these viruses can trigger a variety of health issues, ranging from asymptomatic diarrhea to critical organ failure. Nonpharmacologic and vaccine therapies have largely been used to treat corona virus illness 2019 (COVID-19) [3-4]. Notwithstanding the fact that NPIs are successful, they have a detrimental effect on everyday life and the economy [5]. In light of the well-established high efficacy of COVID-19 booster doses a dose of the vaccine administered six months after the completion of a primary series, out of which one of the most extensive and well-established bodies of evidence in critical illness supports the management of severe SARS-CoV-2 infection [6-7]. Effective management of this condition has been achieved through the use of immunomodulatory treatments (such as corticosteroids, interleukin-6 antagonists, and Janus kinase inhibitors), administration of recombinant antibodies in patients lacking antibodies, and the provision of non-invasive respiratory support.

Early in the illness, high-risk people can see a reduction in disease development due to the use of antiviral medicines (e.g., remdesivir and molnupiravir) [8]. However, due to the late onset of hypoxemia in the majority of patients admitted to the intensive care unit, these drugs are not particularly successful in controlling the condition. Although not backed by dependable data, remdesivir might be beneficial for persons with severe immunosuppression [9]. In severe COVID-19 cases, infections acquired in the intensive care unit (ICU), including bacterial and fungal infections, are relatively common, while bacterial co-infections contracted from the community are quite uncommon. As additional evidence becomes available, clinicians ought to consistently consult the evolving management circumstances of COVID-19 [10].

Antiviral drugs are those that function to combat viral infections. Antiviral drugs are currently ineffective against a wide range of viral infections. A number of antiviral drugs exert their effects through the inhibition of viral replication. Due to the fact that viruses proliferate within cells by using the metabolic processes of the host cell, antiviral drugs can only target a limited number of metabolic processes. Originally designed to combat Alphavirus infections, Molnupiravir is an orally administered antiviral drug with a wide spectrum of activity. However, it has now been modified for the treatment of COVID-19 disease, which is caused by the nasopharyngeal SARS-CoV-2 virus. Molnupiravir has been granted emergency use authorization status by the European Medicines Agency (EMA) to treat mild-to-moderate COVID-19 in adults who have tested positive for the virus via direct SARS-CoV-2 viral testing [11-15].

HPLC, which enables rapid, inexpensive, precise, and accurate analysis, is one of the most often utilized analytical techniques in pharmaceutical research [16]. The literature describes an LC-MS/MS method for identifying molnupiravir and its metabolite in human plasma and sputum [17]. Nevertheless, an established methodology for quantifying molnupiravir in various pharmacological dosage forms has yet to be documented. This study aimed to establish a quick, selective, accurate, precise, and durable Reverse Phase High-Performance Liquid Chromatography (RP-HPLC) technique for detecting molnupiravir in transport samples. The method that was developed was subjected to comprehensive validation in strict adherence to ICH recommendations [18].

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Chemicals and Reagents

The analytical grade reagents, chemicals, and solvents were used and bought from Loba Chemie and SD Fine-Chem Limited (SDFCL). The standard Molnupiravir was procured from Lupin Ltd as a gift sample.

2.2. Instrumentation and chromatographic conditions

The chromatographic separations were performed using a Shimadzu HPLC System. This system is equipped with a Shimadzu LC-20AD fluid delivery device (Pump) and a diode array detector for detection purposes. Additionally, the system includes a column oven (Shimadzu CTO-20AC) and an auto-sampler (Shimadzu SIL-20AC). The HPLC System is controlled by Lab Solutions (Version 1.25) software. The separation of the analyte was conducted on a C18 column (Thermo Fisher Scientific HS-C18, with dimension 250 mm × 4.6 mm, 5 μm particle size) employing an isocratic elution of H₂O: ACN (70:30, V/V) at a column temperature of 30°C. The mobile phase flowed at a rate of 1.0 ml/min. For finding, the wavelength was fixed at 234 nm, and the sample injection volume was 10 μL. The run time was 30 min for the analysis.

2.3. Preparation of Standard stock solutions

A standard stock solution of Molnupiravir was made by liquefying 10 mg of Molnupiravir in 10 ml of the diluent (mobile phase), resulting in a concentration of 1 mg/ml. Following this, 1 ml of the prepared solution was transferred and further diluted to a volume of 10 ml with diluent in a 10 ml volumetric flask, resulting in the generation of the Molnupiravir standard stock solution at a concentration of 100 μg/ml. The standard solutions were kept at 4 °C and utilized for HPLC analysis.

2.4. Establishing calibration criteria:

The prepared stock solution was diluted by way of the mobile phase solution to generate calibration reference solutions (10, 20, 30, 40 and 50 μg/mL). The dilutions were made through adding the mobile phase combination with the stock solution.

2.5. System Suitability:

System suitability was assessed using a standard solution prepared by injecting the Molnupiravir standard stock solution (100 μg/ml) into the HPLC system under the defined chromatographic conditions. The subsequent parameters were assessed in order to verify the proper functioning of the system: Percentage Relative Standard Deviation (RSD) should be ≤ 2%, theoretical plates ≥ 2000 and Tailing Factor between 0.85 to 2.0.

2.6. Method Validation:

The reliability and accuracy of the developed HPLC method for Molnupiravir analysis were rigorously assessed through a systematic method validation process as per the ICH Q2 (R1) guidelines. This essential step ensures that the analytical procedure is suitable for its intended purpose and complies with regulatory requirements. The method validation was performed for the linearity, accuracy, precision, specificity, selectivity, and sensitivity (limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantification (LOQ) [19-32].

2.6.1. Linearity and Range:

The method's linearity was assessed by constructing a calibration curve with a range of standard solutions at varying concentrations (10 to 50 μg/mL). The range of the method was established to cover the expected concentration range in the samples. Measurements were taken in triplicate and plotted on a linear regression graph of mean peak area against concentration. The derived linear regression equation was then used for subsequent calculations.

2.6.2. Accuracy:

The method's accuracy was evaluated by calculating the percentage recovery of Molnupiravir at various concentration levels (80–120%) using the standard addition method. This analysis was performed in triplicate. In the recovery experiments, a known quantity of the standard was added at three different levels (spike level-1 (80%), spike level-2 (100%), and spike level-3 (120%)) to a previously known concentration standard. The percentage recovery for each spiked level was then determined.

2.6.3. Precision:

The precision of the method was assessed through studies of repeatability and intermediate precision using standard solutions. Repeatability was evaluated by performing six consecutive injections of the standard solution. Intraday precision involved analyzing replicates ($n = 6$) of the standard solutions on the same day, whereas interday precision was examined over five consecutive days ($n = 6$). The results of precision were reported as % relative standard deviation (RSD) $\leq 2\%$. Peak area responses with a % RSD $\leq 2\%$ were deemed acceptable.

2.6.4. Limit of Detection and Limit of Quantification:

In accordance with ICH guidelines, the detection and quantification limits of the developed method were determined using the standard deviation of the response and the slope of the calibration curve. These parameters indicate the method's sensitivity and ability to detect low levels of Molnupiravir

Limit of detection = $3.3 \times \sigma / S$,

Limit of quantification = $10 \times \sigma / S$,

where σ is the standard deviation of the response and S is the slope.

2.6.5. Robustness:

Robustness studies involved intentionally altering key method parameters like the composition of the mobile phase, flow rate, and column temperature to evaluate their effects on the method's performance, ensuring its consistency and reliability under varied conditions.

2.7. Assay:

20 capsules were precisely measured and then powdered content collected. After being finding out average weight of content of each capsule, powder equivalent to 10 mg of the drug was mixed with 10 mL of water and sonicated for 15 minutes. Following filtering, a solution comprising 1000 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ of molnupiravir was obtained. Then after series dilution the solution of Molnupiravir was made with a final concentration of 20 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ from the above-mentioned solution. Then it was filtered through the 0.45 μ syringe filter and injected to HPLC column.

2.8. Specificity:

The specificity of the method was assessed by testing the detection of molnupiravir amidst possible impurities and excipients. Forced degradation studies were conducted to assess the method's ability to distinguish the analyte from its degradation products. The specificity of the method can be demonstrated by subjecting a Molnupiravir to acid, alkaline, oxidative, and photolytic degradation. After subjecting the Molnupiravir to these conditions, analyzes the primary peak for peak purity indicates that the approach successfully separates the degradation products from the pure active component. ("ICH, Q1A (R2) stability testing of new drug substances and products," 1996)

2.8.1. Hydrolytic degradation

Hydrolytic stress testing was carried out to stimulate the degradation of the drug substance and generate its principal degradation products. This involves subjecting the molnupiravir in neutral, acidic, and basic environments over a defined period of time.

In the experiment, 100 μL of the molnupiravir standard stock (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was diluted to 1000 μL by adding either 0.1 M HCl or 0.1 M NaOH. This mixture was then maintained at 60°C for 30 minutes. Afterward, the solutions were cooled to room temperature and neutralized with the appropriate amount of either HCl or NaOH. Subsequently, they were diluted with the mobile phase to achieve a concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ and injected into the HPLC system for analysis.

2.8.2. Oxidative degradation

For the experiment, 100 μL of the molnupiravir standard stock (100 $\mu\text{g/mL}$) was diluted to 1000 μL using 3 percent H_2O_2 . The resulting solution was then incubated at 60°C for 30 minutes. After dilution with the mobile phase to a final concentration of 10 $\mu\text{g/mL}$, the solutions were injected into the HPLC system for analysis.

2.8.3. Photolytic Degradation

In the experiment, 100 μL of the molnupiravir standard stock (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$) was expanded to 1000 μL . This solution was then exposed to UV light for one day at room temperature. Subsequently, it was further diluted with the mobile phase to achieve a 10 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ concentration, before being injected into the HPLC system for analysis.

3. Results And Discussion

3.1. Method Development:

3.1.1. Optimization of Chromatographic Conditions

To measure molnupiravir in formulation as well as bulk, a novel RP-HPLC method has been developed. Maintaining the peak of chromatographic efficiency during the course of the experiment is crucial when it comes to molnupiravir detection and measurement. Over the course of the development process, numerous experimental trials have been planned in order to obtain a discriminating RP-HPLC methodology, (Figure 1). The RP-HPLC method involves various chromatographic conditions including the selection of the suitable stationary phase, determination of the method type (isocratic or gradient), and setting the mobile phase ratio, flow rate, and detection wavelength. The optimization of these chromatographic conditions is outlined as follows. A standard solution of Molnupiravir was used for the method development, (Figure 2).

Figure 1: UV Spectrum of Molnupiravir

Figure 2 : Chromatogram of Molnupiravir at optimized chromatographic condition.

3.1.2. Selection of stationary phase

For the selection of the stationary phase, carbon load and surface area were considered. The Thermo Fisher Scientific Discovery HS C18 Column was selected for method development of molnupiravir. The column had a 20% carbon loading and a 300 m^2/g surface area.

3.1.3. Influence of mobile phase and organic modifier

Within the scientific literature, suggestions were made to use water, acetonitrile, and methanol as components of the mobile phase in order to separate Molnupiravir by chromatography. Initially, an attempt was made with gradient elution, but alas, the baseline proved unstable, and the retention time (RT) of Molnupiravir soared to undesirable heights. Consequently, the gradient elution method was dismissed. Various isocratic combinations of mobile phases were tested in an effort to find the best separation. While methanol often stands as a cost-effective choice for quantifying various compounds, it did not align with the chromatographic needs of Molnupiravir. This prompted a contemplation of the organic content within the mobile phase. The substitution of methanol with acetonitrile emerged as a transformative decision, enhancing the overall chromatographic conditions. The effect of the acetonitrile concentration in the acetonitrile: water mobile phase on the retention time of Molnupiravir was carefully studied. Concurrently, changes in the water concentration were thoroughly investigated. After a series of meticulous trials, the combination of acetonitrile: water emerged as the catalyst for favourable chromatographic conditions. The envisaged outcome, characterised by optimum resolution and a concise analysis time, materialised with this mobile phase amalgamation. Consequently, acetonitrile: water were affirmed as the chosen mobile phase for the entirety of the experiments.

3.1.4. Influence of Flow rate

The efficient separation of desired components is significantly influenced by the mobile phase's flow rate. Different flow rates, varying from 0.5 to 1.5 ml/min, were systematically explored to find the optimal flow rate for the separation of molnupiravir. Significantly, increasing the flow rate led to a faster elution of the Molnupiravir, but this did not produce a noticeable separation of the intended product. Significant progress was made when the flow rate was set at 1.0 ml/min. A clear, symmetrical peak appeared in the chromatographic profile, indicating that the intended product had been separated correctly and precisely.

3.1.5. Influence of Detection Wavelength

The meticulous choice of a scanning wavelength held paramount significance in the experiments geared towards detecting molnupiravir. The UV spectrum of Molnupiravir in water-ACN mixtures of 70:30 v/v showed the presence of ACN in the wavelength range from 200 to 400 nm. Notably, molnupiravir exhibited its peak absorption at 234 nm, as discerned from this spectral exploration. Based on this, the wavelength (234 nm) that corresponds to Molnupiravir's maximum absorption was carefully chosen as the best measurement wavelength for Molnupiravir analysis in the mobile phase. This meticulous selection ensured precise and effective analysis of Molnupiravir in the experimental setup.

Ultimately, to develop the RP-HPLC method for molnupiravir quantification, the impacts of the stationary phase, mobile phase, flow rate, and detection wavelength were all examined. The Thermo Fisher Scientific Discovery HS-C18 Column was chosen as the stationary phase for the chromatographic analysis. Acetonitrile mixed with water in a 70:30 (v/v) ratio was used as the mobile phase, with a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The analysis of the samples was conducted at a wavelength of 234 nm. The retention time of Molnupiravir was found to be 3.5 min.

3.2. Analytical method validation:

The RP-HPLC method developed was validated in accordance with ICH guidelines. We studied the developed method's Linearity, Accuracy, Precision, Sensitivity, Specificity, and Selectivity.

3.2.1. Linearity:

In order to determine the operational range and determine the linearity of the calibration curve, it was crucial to analyse the detector response at different concentrations of the utilised standard. Regression analysis was harnessed to scrutinize the linearity of the developed RP-HPLC method, employing the equation $y = bx + c$. Herein, x denoted the concentration of the standard solution in micrograms per milliliter ($\mu\text{g/mL}$), while y represented the corresponding peak area. The parameters b , the slope of the line, and c , the intercept of the straight line with the y -axis, played pivotal roles in this assessment. Within the purview of this study, linearity underwent meticulous evaluation across the concentration

spectrum of 10-50 $\mu\text{g/mL}$ for the standard solution of Molnupiravir (Table 1). The resultant calibration curve exhibited a linear trajectory within this concentration range, accompanied by an exemplary display of linear regression, as depicted in (Figure 3). This demonstrated the linearity of the RP-HPLC method that was specifically designed for the study of Molnupiravir.

Table 1: Linearity Study of Molnupiravir

Concentration of [$\mu\text{g/mL}$]	Peak area [Mean $\pm$ SD; n = 3]	% RSD
10	872427 $\pm$ 904	0.103
20	1803616 $\pm$ 1576	0.087
30	2585095 $\pm$ 2966	0.114
40	3432496 $\pm$ 1245	0.036
50	4304998 $\pm$ 2837	0.065

Figure 3: Calibration curve of Molnupiravir

3.2.1. System suitability:

To evaluate the robustness and dependability of the developed RP-HPLC method for Molnupiravir analysis, a system suitability test was performed. The outcomes exhibited outstanding performance in all significant criteria. It was determined that the resolution of Molnupiravir and its associated compounds exceeded 2.0, thereby guaranteeing satisfactory separation. The retention time demonstrated stability, and the symmetry factor for the Molnupiravir peaks approached the ideal value of 1.0, suggesting that the chromatographic peaks were well-shaped. The theoretical plate and tailing factor values fell within acceptable ranges, indicating that the chromatographic system operated efficiently. In addition, the small relative standard deviation (RSD) of peak regions resulting from several injections of the standard solution demonstrates the method's precision. The aforementioned findings collectively validate the RP-HPLC method's capability to accurately and dependably analyse pharmaceutical formulations containing molnupiravir. The results obtained are represented in the (Figure 4) – (Figure 5), (Table 2).

Figure 4 :Chromatogram of Molnupiravir

Figure 5: Peak purity Profile

Table 2. System Suitability Parameters

Drug name	Peak area	Retention time	Theoretical plate	Tailing factor	Peak purity index	Single point threshold
Molnupiravir	1806406	3.529	7736	1.477	0.9999	0.906729

3.2.3. Precision:

The precision of the RP-HPLC method that was developed for the quantification of molnupiravir was methodically evaluated by conducting experiments on repeatability and intermediate precision. The outcomes of the repeatability test, which was performed by successively injecting the standard solution six times, were very constant. Under identical conditions, the relative standard deviation (RSD) of peak regions for Molnupiravir remained remarkably small, validating the method's precision. The intermediate precision research involved the replication of the analysis by many analysts on separate days, so guaranteeing a thorough assessment of the precision of the procedure. The RSD values for Molnupiravir peak regions were constantly within acceptable ranges under a variety of settings, demonstrating the RP-HPLC method's dependability and reproducibility. The cumulative outcomes of these precision investigations serve to strengthen the method's ability to generate reliable and consistent results, thereby confirming its suitability for the study of Molnupiravir in pharmaceutical formulations. The results obtained are represented in (Table 3), (Table 4), (Table 5).

Table 3: Repeatability studies of Molnupiravir

Sr. No.	Peak area
1	1801206
2	1802765
3	1804522
4	1807865
5	1805560
6	1811406
Mean	1805554
SD	3669.75
% RSD	0.203

Table 4 : Precision (Intra-Day) studies of Molnupiravir

Time interval	Peak area	Mean	SD	% RSD
1	1806406	1805226	3387.412	0.187
2	1807865			
3	1801406			

Table 5: Precision Precision (Inter-Day) studies of Molnupiravir

Day	Peak area	Mean	SD	% RSD
1	1815235	1812507	4122.425	0.227
2	1807765			
3	1814522			

3.2.4. Robustness:

The rigorous investigation of the proposed RP-HPLC method's robustness for the study of molnupiravir involved the deliberate modification of crucial chromatographic parameters. A variety of experimental settings were investigated in order to assess the robustness of the approach against slight alterations. Minor modifications to the proportion of mobile phase were implemented as variations in the composition of the mobile phase were introduced. Furthermore, intentional variations in both the flow rate and column temperature were introduced. The reaction of the approach to these alterations was thoroughly examined, and the consequences for critical parameters like retention time, theoretical plate, and tailing factor were determined.

The results indicated that the RP-HPLC method exhibited a robust performance, maintaining the integrity of chromatographic separation even under varied conditions. The method's capacity to maintain its reliability and usefulness for molnupiravir analysis despite minor variations in experimental settings is indicated by the low impact on important parameters. The aforementioned resilience serves to emphasize the adaptability and consistency of the RP-HPLC technique in the context of pharmaceutical quality control. The results obtained are represented in (Table 6).

Table 6: Robustness studies of Molnupiravir

Change in Flow-rate						
Sr. no	Flow rate (ml/min)	Retention factor	peak area	Mean	SD	%RSD
1	0.9	3.956	1815856	1808565	7316.132	0.404
2	1	3.529	1808616			
3	1.1	3.484	1801224			

Change in Mobile Phase ratio						
Sr. no	Ratio (v/v %)	Retention factor	peak area	Mean	SD	%RSD
1	65:35	4.125	1813746	1807110	5977.192	0.330
2	70:30	3.519	1805435			
3	75:25	2.989	1802149			
Change in Wavelength						
Sr. no	Wavelength (λ) (nm)	Retention factor	peak area	Mean	SD	%RSD
1	229	3.527	1750546	1765890	33746.76	1.911
2	234	3.550	1804582			
3	239	3.556	1742541			

3.2.5. Accuracy:

The accuracy of the RP-HPLC method for molnupiravir quantification was comprehensively evaluated to assess its capability to provide results close to the true values. This required a comparison between the concentrations of Molnupiravir that were measured and those that were known to be present in the standard solutions that were generated. The recovery experiment was carried out by supplementing a pharmaceutical formulation with predetermined quantities of Molnupiravir; the resulting samples were subsequently subjected to RP-HPLC analysis. The percentage recovery was computed by comparing the concentrations that were actually measured to those that were anticipated. The results demonstrated a high degree of accuracy, with the percentage recovery falling within an acceptable range. This indicates that the RP-HPLC method is capable of providing precise and reliable molnupiravir quantification in pharmaceutical formulations, affirming its suitability for quality control applications in the pharmaceutical industry. Accuracy studies of molnupiravir represent in (Table 7).

Table 7 : Accuracy studies of Molnupiravir

% Level	Concentration	% Recovery	Mean	SD	% RSD
80%	36	99.3089	99.73367	0.815171	0.817348
	36	100.6735			
	36	99.2186			
100 %	40	100.3480	99.80696	0.599230	0.600389
	40	99.1629			
	40	99.9100			
120%	44	101.4933	101.3116	0.225449	0.22253
	44	101.3822			
	44	101.0593			

3.2.6. LOD and LOQ:

To determine the sensitivity of the RP-HPLC method in Molnupiravir analysis, the limits of detection (LOD) also limits of quantitation (LOQ) were carefully determined. The lowest concentration of molnupiravir that could be accurately and reliably detected but not necessarily quantified was known as the LOD, while the lowest concentration that could be quantified with reasonable precision and accuracy was known as the LOQ. By progressively diluting the standard molnupiravir solution, injections were made until the signal-to-noise ratio reached a value corresponding to the LOD and LOQ. The findings demonstrated the method's confidence in its ability to detect low quantities of the analyte, as the LOD and LOQ for Molnupiravir were reached at values that permitted sensitive and accurate quantification. The LOD and LOQ was found to be 4.058 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ & 13.5095 $\mu\text{g/ml}$ respectively.

3.3. Assay:

3.3.1. % Assay determination of Molnupiravir Marketed Formulation

The assay performance of the RP-HPLC method for molnupiravir analysis was rigorously evaluated to determine its accuracy in quantifying the active pharmaceutical ingredient within a pharmaceutical formulation. Sample of formulations containing molnupiravir were analysed as part of the test to determine the method's capacity to yield accurate and consistent results.

The percentage assay was computed by comparing the real molnupiravir content in the samples to the theoretical value. The measured molnupiravir content nearly matched the predicted values, suggesting a high degree of accuracy, according to the results. When determining the test of molnupiravir in pharmaceutical formulations, the RP-HPLC method's precision and reproducibility were highlighted by the low relative standard deviation (RSD) observed in the assay results, represent in (Table 8).

Table 8: Assay studies of Molnupiravir

Sample	% Recovery	Mean	SD	% RSD
1	98.9583	100.2614	1.2345	1.231
2	99.9663			
3	99.2765			
4	101.5044			
5	101.6016			

3.4. Stability:

The stability and susceptibility of molnupiravir to different stress conditions were evaluated by degradation tests, which yielded vital information regarding its possible degradation pathways. The primary aim was to simulate and comprehend the behavior of molnupiravir under various storage and environmental conditions. This research would contribute to the development of suitable storage guidelines and the estimation of the drug's shelf life.

Molnupiravir was subjected to a variety of degradation conditions, including acid hydrolysis, base hydrolysis, oxidation, and photolytic degradation, in order to conduct forced degradation studies. Later, the samples collected under these stress circumstances were analysed using the RP-HPLC. The outcomes in Table. 9 revealed the RP-HPLC method resilience in segregating molnupiravir from its degradation byproducts, hence enabling the evaluation of degradation levels in both qualitative and quantitative terms. The results of this study provide significant insights into the stability profile of molnupiravir when subjected to stress. This knowledge aids in the establishment of storage and handling guidelines for pharmaceutical products.

Table 9: Stability studies of Molnupiravir

Sr.no	Degradation Condition	% Drug Undegraded	% Drug Degraded
1	Acid	41.1879	58.8121
2	Alkali	93.8524	6.1476
3	Photo stability	94.6274	5.3726
4	Oxidation	100	0

4. Conclusion:

To achieve a sufficient separation of eluted chemicals, HPLC settings were optimized. In order to obtain a symmetric and stable peak, several mobile phase compositions were initially tested. Based on peak characteristics (height, tailing, theoretical plates, run time, etc.), the mobile phase and flow rate were chosen. The method proved to be quite robust when using water: acetonitrile (70:30% V/V) mixture as the mobile phase and maintaining a flow rate of 1.0 ml/min. The ideal wavelength for finding was 234 nm, where a higher detector reaction for molnupiravir was achieved. The testified average retention time (Rt) for molnupiravir was 3.52 min. USP 28 (621) states that system appropriateness assessments are crucial component of chromatographic methods. These parameters

are employed to verify the reproducibility of the chromatographic system. System suitability tests were performed to determine its efficacy, and it was discovered that all the parameters were inside the acceptable range. Low results for %RSD show that the approach is accurate and precise. The recovery for molnupiravir was determined to be 99.73%, 99.80% and 101.31%, demonstrating the efficacy of the suggested technique. Molnupiravir showed linearity in the concentration range of 10–50 µg/ml, with a drug regression of 0.9991. Molnupiravir limit of detection and limit quantification were revealed to be 4.0528µg/ml and 13.5095µg/ml, respectively. The suggested approach is straightforward, delicate, exact, particular, accurate, and repeatable. The outcomes of the validation parameters indicate that the analytical method is suitable for its intended purpose and meets the criteria established in ICH Q2 (R1).

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Conflict of Interest:

Authors declare no conflict of Interest

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Abbreviations

SARS-CoV-2: Severe acute respiratory syndrome coronavirus 2;

COVID-19: coronavirus disease 2019;

PDA: Photodiode Array detector

RP-HPLC: Reverse-phase high-performance liquid chromatography;

NHC: N-hydroxycytidine

ICH: International Conference on Harmonization;

LOD: Limit of detection;

LOQ: Limit of quantification

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